

USING FLUTTER TO CREATE MOBILE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract: This article presents the reforms in the educational process, the work being carried out in our republic and the use of Flutter in creating mobile applications, the sequence of using Flutter widgets in creating mobile applications. The importance of digital educational resources in school education is very great, which serves to improve the quality of the educational process, enhance interactivity and personal development of students. This ensures interactivity and visual presentation of education, that is, digital educational resources (video lessons, animations, simulations) help students understand complex concepts in a visual and practical way, which is especially effective in STEM subjects (mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology).

Keywords: educational reforms, online education, mobile technologies, mobile applications, Flutter framework, Flutter widgets, e-learning platforms.

INTRODUCTION

A legal space has been created commensurate with the new stage of Uzbekistan's development and modern trends in the field of education. In particular, the legal status of teachers was firmly established for the first time in the newly amended Constitution of the country. According to it, "In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the work of a teacher is recognized as the basis for the development of society and the state, the formation and upbringing of a healthy, harmonious generation, the preservation and enrichment of the spiritual and cultural potential

of the people. The state takes care of the protection of the honor and dignity of teachers, their social and material well-being, and professional growth” (Article 52) [1]. Also, based on today's requirements, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” was adopted in a new edition [2]. In addition, our Basic Law provides for specific mechanisms aimed at expanding the opportunities for children with disabilities to receive quality education as a special obligation of the state in the field of education. In particular, Article 50 of the Constitution introduces a social norm on the provision of inclusive education for children with special educational needs in educational institutions.

An analysis of the reforms implemented in the education system in the country in a historically short period of time shows that positive trends have emerged. The approach to the education sector has changed radically. In particular, the development of school education under the slogan “New Uzbekistan begins at the school threshold” has become a nationwide movement. The workload in schools has been optimized, and the practice of involving teachers in forced labor has been abolished. In this regard, traditional approaches have been abandoned, and modern technologies and advanced foreign experience have been actively introduced.

The basis of the reforms in the education system was to raise the status of teachers in society and radically change the attitude towards them. In this regard, material support for teachers was provided, including the provision of preferential loans to them, and the introduction of bonuses for teachers working in remote regions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Today, under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, comprehensive strategic reforms are being implemented in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy was approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-6079 dated October 5, 2020, which is a comprehensive document aimed at

accelerating the digital economy, information and communication technologies (ICT) and the digitalization of the education system in the country. This strategy includes the following main areas for the development of Internet infrastructure, training personnel in the ICT sector and digitalization of the education system:

- it is planned to establish centers for the provision and export of remote services using ICT in the regions. This is intended to develop IT outsourcing services and strengthen local infrastructure;

- it is planned to organize ICT training courses for students in grades 5–11 of general education schools by establishing digital technology training centers in each city and district;

- it is aimed at improving the quality of computer science education by encouraging the active participation of organizations in the field of information technology in the educational process;

- it is planned to improve digital governance in the education sector by creating an information system for managing access rights to information systems for employees of the education inspectorate [3].

In order to address this issue, a new program is being implemented starting in 2023. According to it, European vocational education standards have been introduced in 1 technical school in each region. In the next five years, all colleges and technical schools will be covered by this system.

At the same time, branches of more than 30 prestigious higher education institutions from foreign countries (USA, Great Britain, Italy, Finland, Korea, India, Singapore, Russia, etc.) have been opened in Uzbekistan.

The importance of digital educational resources in school education is very great, as they serve to improve the quality of the educational process, enhance interactivity, and promote the personal development of students. This ensures interactivity and visual presentation of education, that is, digital educational resources (video lessons, animations, simulations) help students understand

complex concepts in a visual and practical way, which is especially effective in STEM subjects (mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology).

The possibility of an individual approach also increases, that is, tasks and resources can be provided that are adapted to the level of knowledge of each student, and programs adapted for children with special needs allow them to receive equal education.

Digital educational resources include online lessons, video tutorials, electronic tests, interactive simulations, and gamified learning platforms.

Mobile technologies are a system of technologies that provide information exchange, processing, and management using wireless communication and portable devices.

Mobile Application is a software application designed to run on a smartphone, tablet or other mobile device. Mobile applications allow users to communicate, receive information, play games, conduct business, get education and perform various other tasks.

Mobile apps can be divided into:

Native apps, which are pre-installed or downloaded but are originally designed for a specific operating system or device. An app written for a device with Apple firmware will not run on a device with Android firmware. Therefore, many developers prepare software products in the form of packages for multiple operating systems.

Web apps. Web apps that are special instances of a mobile browser for viewing specially designed mobile sites. They work in web programming languages: HTML markup, formal CSS and embedded JavaScript. The advantage is that applications are independent of the device's operating system, since the data is mainly stored "in the cloud" and processed using World Wide Web resources. The disadvantage is that they are slower than the corresponding native applications.

Hybrid applications. Hybrid applications are a mixture of the two

approaches described above. Hybrid applications are created using the WebView component. Webview applications are mobile versions of websites displayed in the mobile application interface. Webview applications are available on Android (Android WebView Media Integrity) and iOS platforms. Such an application can display a site created using web application technology. For the user, such an application looks native and has all the necessary functionality. For the developer, using this technology reduces the cost of writing separate code for the mobile application, since the site already provides all the necessary functionality using web application technology. Web view apps can also take advantage of iOS and Android's push notifications, payments via GooglePay or ApplePay, and many other features. These sub-types of apps are developed using frameworks such as Cordova, Flutter, React Native, and others.

Cross-platform apps. These types of apps are sometimes confused with hybrid apps. These apps are developed using cross-platform frameworks such as React Native (JavaScript), Flutter (Dart), Ionic (JavaScript), Xamarin (.NET and C#), and have common code for both iOS and Android.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Buttons are the graphical control element that **provides a user to trigger an event** such as taking actions, making choices, searching things, and many more. They can be placed anywhere in our UI like dialogs, forms, cards, toolbars, etc.

Buttons are the Flutter widgets, which is a part of the material design library. Flutter provides several types of buttons that have different shapes, styles, and features. The standard features of a button in Flutter are given below: We can easily apply themes on buttons, shapes, color, animation, and behavior; We can also theme icons and text inside the button; Buttons can be composed of different child widgets for different characteristics. Following are the different types of button available in Flutter: Flat Button; Raised Button; Floating Button; Drop Down Button; Icon Button; Inkwell Button; PopupMenu Button; Outline Button.

Let us discuss each button in detail.

1. Flat Button

It is a **text label button** that does not have much decoration and displayed **without any elevation**. The flat button has two required properties that are: **child and onPressed()**. It is mostly used in toolbars, dialogs, or inline with other content. By default, the flat button has no color, and its text is black. But, we can use color to the button and text using **color and textColor** attributes, respectively.

Example:

Open the **main.dart** file and replace it with the below code.

```
import 'package:flutter/material.dart';
void main() { runApp(MyApp()); }
class MyApp extends StatefulWidget {
  @override
  MyAppState createState() => _MyAppState(); }
class _MyAppState extends State<MyApp> {
  @override
  Widget build(BuildContext context) {
    return MaterialApp(
      home: Scaffold(
        appBar: AppBar(
          title: Text('Flutter FlatButton Example'), ),
        body: Center(child: Column(children: <Widget>[
          Container( margin: EdgeInsets.all(25),
            child: FlatButton( child: Text('SignUp', style: TextStyle(fontSize: 20.0)),
              onPressed: ( ) { }, ), ),
          Container( margin: EdgeInsets.all(25),
            child: FlatButton(
```



```
child: Text('LogIn', style: TextStyle(fontSize: 20.0),),
color: Colors.blueAccent,
textColor: Colors.white,
onPressed: () {},
), ), ] ) ) , ); } }
```

Output:

If we run this app, we will see the following screen:

2. Raised Button

It is a button, which is based on the material widget and has a **rectangular body**. It is similar to a flat button, but it **has an elevation** that will increase when the button is pressed. It adds dimension to the UI along Z-axis. It has several properties like text color, shape, padding, button color, the color of a button when disabled, animation time, elevation, etc.

This button has **two callback functions**.

onPressed(): It is triggered when the button is pressed.

onLongPress(): It is triggered when the button is long pressed.

It is to note that this button is in a **disabled state** if `onPressed()` and `onLongPressed()` callbacks are not specified.

3. Floating Action Button. A FAB button is a **circular icon button** that triggers the primary action in our application. It is the most used button in today's applications. We can use this button for adding, refreshing, or sharing the content. Flutter suggests using at most one FAB button per screen. There are two types of Floating Action Button: **FloatingActionButton:** It creates a simple circular floating button with a child widget inside it. It must have a child parameter to display a widget. **FloatingActionButton.extended:** It creates a wide floating button along with an icon and a label inside it. Instead of a child, it uses labels and icon parameters.

4. DropDown Button. A drop-down button is used to create a nice overlay on

the screen that allows the user to select any item from multiple options. Flutter allows a simple way to implement a drop-down box or drop-down button. This button shows the currently selected item and an arrow that opens a menu to select an item from multiple options.

Flutter provides a **DropDownButton widget** to implement a drop-down list. We can place it anywhere in our app.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the reforms in the educational process, the work being carried out in our republic, have reached several high levels. We can see that the creation of electronic educational resources in the educational process and the role of mobile applications in this is also increasing, and for this, the sequence of using Flutter in creating mobile applications, and using Flutter widgets in creating mobile applications is of great importance. The use of mobile applications in the educational process serves to increase the quality and efficiency of education.

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